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TEACHING CONTENT OF SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS IN TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15093652>

In higher education institutions, in the process of preparing future teachers for their future professional activities, specialized and specialized subjects are taught. The subjects taught in the direction of technological education prepare future teachers for this profession by providing information about these subjects. This is done in the process of education. As is known, education is a two-way process, covering the activities of educators and learners. The effectiveness of this process is largely determined by the correct orientation of the activities of educators and learners. It is customary to call and name this path in pedagogical science as teaching methods. Namely, teaching methods are a way of carrying out activities that lead to achieving the intended goal.

Today, the training of specialists who can compete and know their field based on the requirements of the times is a requirement of the time. A modern specialist should be a person who is knowledgeable in his profession, able to improve it in the future and thereby develop socio-economic development. One of the urgent tasks facing the education system is to train comprehensively qualified specialists, to form in them competencies for the wide use of modern pedagogical technologies. The quality of training qualified specialists in educational institutions is largely determined by the effective teaching of specialized subjects. The content of specialized subjects should correspond to the description of a particular direction or specialty, that is, they should cover the methods of activity performed in the profession of the student. Specialized subjects form theoretical and practical knowledge, training and skills in a specific specialty; develop skills in creating, accumulating and using a knowledge base in the specialty; should provide scientific knowledge, practical training and skills in modeling processes and a systematic approach to achieving the desired results of professional activity in the specialty.

In particular, there are several dozen specialties and specializations in the direction of technological education, which are intended to be taught continuously during the educational process based on consistent content.

In the bachelor's degree in technological education 60112300, such disciplines as "Technology Education Methodology", "Educational Work Methodology", "Professional Competence", "Professional Guidance", "Folk Crafts and Artistic Design", "Technology Education Practicum", "Fundamentals of Robotics", "Technology and Design", "Automated Systems for the Construction and Modeling of Sewing Products" are defined as specialties and specializations.

Students studying in higher education institutions are required to deeply understand the content and essence of the methods of organizing educational and learning activities, taking into account their further activities in mastering specialized subjects. After all, in the context of educational methods, each method serves to establish its own unique educational and learning activities, to show ways to transfer educational materials and master them.

The external appearance of the joint activities of the participants in the educational process, that is, the teacher and students, carried out in a certain established manner, represents the organizational form of technological education. Educational methods play an important role in the effective organization of the educational process. Educational methods serve to clarify the goal of education, with the help of which the ways of mastering the content of education are expressed, the interaction of the teacher and students is reflected, the nature of the interaction. The method, firstly, is manifested as a means of achieving the goal of education, and secondly, it is a condition for the implementation of educational activities.

So, teaching specialized subjects should be understood as the presentation, transmission of information in the specialty and specialized subjects taught in the direction of technological education by the teacher in the process of teaching, and the way in which this information, theories are perceived and mastered by the students (students).

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